

VMAT versus DCAT radiotherapy planning in SBRT Brain

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Abstract

VMAT and DCAT radiotherapy plans were generated with the Monaco 5.1 treatment planning system for six PTVs of five Brain cancer patients. The study aimed to compare the dose distributions of the two treatment planning methods. The dose fields were compared with 3DGamma index analysis.

Good agreement in dose fields (3DGamma index >90%, 3% dose and 3 mm distance correspondence) was found if no OAR nearby the PTV was present, while the VMAT plans were superior in sparing the OARs

Introduction

During the VMAT treatments, the requested dose distribution is produced by moving the MLC leaves and by variation of the dose rate, while during the dynamic arc therapy (DCAT), the MLC leaves follow the shape of the PTV, and the dose rate is modulated with the arc angle.

The study aimed to compare the dose field agreement of the two treatment planning methods.

Materials and methods

Five patients with small Brain tumor were selected. The volume of the PTV, the OARs being in the proximity of the PTV, and the prescribed dose are summarized in Table 1. Single-fraction VMAT and DCAT SBRT plans were generated with the Monaco 5.1 treatment planning system. The beam setup was: three 6MV arcs with 0, 45, and 90 degrees collimator rotation. The same beam setup and restrictions were applied for the two planning methods, but in DCAT plans, the field margins were reduced from 7 to 2mm. The dose distributions were compared with 3D Gamma index analysis performed with the Verisoft ver .6.2 software (PTW, Germany). The reference dose field was the VMAT plan, and the DCAT dose matrix was compared using 3% dose and 3mm distance correspondence. We also investigated the dose agreement limited for the high-dose region, with increased suppression value from 5% to 50% of the prescribed dose.

Pat #	tumor vol. ccm	prescription dose Gy	OAR
1	13,3	15	
2	27	15	Brainstem, Nervus opticus
3a	2,5	18	(PTV2)
3b	8,9	18	(PTV1)
4	10,2	15	Brainstem
5	7,4	18	

Table 1. The patient data

Results

The result of the 3DGamma analysis is summarized in Table 2.

Pat#	supression	level
	5,00%	50,00%
1	95,6	96,9
2	86,5	96,1
3a	92,1	98,9
3b	87,7	97,4
4	73,5	86,7
5	94,5	91,5

Table 2. The 3D Gamma indexes [%] with low (5%) and increased (50%) suppression levels

Patient #1: no OAR was in the proximity of the PTV, showed good dose field agreement (3D Gamma index >90%) at the high and at the low dose region too.

Patient #2: OARs were present nearby of the PTV good dose field agreement at the high dose region, while moderate one (3D Gamma index <90%) at the lower dose region.

Patient #3 had two PTVs 3.5cm apart. Good dose agreement was found at the high dose regions, while moderate one in #3b. Restriction was applied to reduce the dose contribution from 3a to 3b.

Patient #4: OARs were present close to the PTV, poor dose field agreement (3D Gamma index <80%) was found at the low dose region.

Patient #5: no OAR was in the proximity of the PTV, showed good dose field agreement at the high and at the low dose region too.

The VMAT plans were more effective in OAR dose sparing than the DCAT ones, resulting in a different dose distributions from the DCAT plans. The majority of the DCAT plans gave significantly lower MU-s to deliver the prescribed dose compared to the VMAT ones, as summarized in Table 3.

Pat#	VMAT MU	DCAT MU	DCAT/VMAT
1	1647	1670	1,01
2	2189	1743	0,8
3a	3524	2165	0,61
3b	2989	1999	0,67
4	3943	1766	0,45
5	2692	2210	0,89

Table 3. The MUs to deliver the prescribed dose in the VMAT and the DCAT plans, and the ratios

Conclusion

The dose fields of the VMAT and DCAT plans showed good agreement at the high dose region. The VMAT plans were superior in sparing OARs being in close proximity of the PTV resulting in a different dose distributions at the low dose region, compared to the DCAT ones. The DCAT plan can be an alternative to the VMAT one, with no significant dose field difference, especially if no OARs are present nearby the PTV. The DCAT plans are oft has the advantage of the lower MU.

The results are consistent with our previous study in stereotactic treatments of Lung cancer

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Appendix

Fig.1 Transversal dose distribution of Patient #1 VMAT and DCAT plans

Fig2. Transversal dose distributions at the isocenter, lateral dose profiles (VMAT- brown DCAT-blue) and the dose difference map.

Volume Analysis

Dose level for evaluation in % of normalization value (= 17.028 Gy) of Data Set B

Dose level	Number of Voxels	Evaluated Voxels	Passed	Failed	Result
10 %	694 002	694 002 (100,0 %)	650 825 (93,8 %)	43 177 (6,2 %)	93,8 % (Green)
30 %	227 786	227 786 (100,0 %)	215 537 (94,6 %)	12 249 (5,4 %)	94,6 % (Green)
50 %	85 670	85 670 (100,0 %)	83 381 (97,3 %)	2 289 (2,7 %)	97,3 % (Green)
70 %	48 232	48 232 (100,0 %)	46 741 (96,9 %)	1 491 (3,1 %)	96,9 % (Green)
80 %	34 809	34 809 (100,0 %)	33 400 (96,0 %)	1 409 (4,0 %)	96,0 % (Green)
85 %	27 600	27 600 (100,0 %)	26 280 (95,2 %)	1 320 (4,8 %)	95,2 % (Green)
90 %	17 798	17 798 (100,0 %)	16 943 (95,2 %)	855 (4,8 %)	95,2 % (Green)
95 %	3 467	3 467 (100,0 %)	3 283 (94,7 %)	184 (5,3 %)	94,7 % (Green)
100 %	1	1 (100,0 %)	0 (0,0 %)	1 (100,0 %)	0,0 % (Red)
>=105 %	0	---	---	---	---

Fig3. 3D Gamma index value of the Patient #1 plans. Reference dose distribution was the VMAT plan.

Fig. 4 The dose distribution of the DCAT and the VMAT plans of the Patient #4, OARs were nearby the PTV

Fig.5. Transversal dose distributions at the isocenter, lateral dose profiles (VMAT- brown and DCAT-blue) and the dose difference map.

Volume Analysis

Dose level for evaluation in % of normalization value (= 19.315 Gy) of Data Set B

Dose level	Number of Voxels	Evaluated Voxels	Passed	Failed	Result
10 %	540 752	540 752 (100,0 %)	389 064 (71,9 %)	151 688 (28,1 %)	71,9 % (Red)
30 %	159 324	159 324 (100,0 %)	97 361 (61,1 %)	61 963 (38,9 %)	61,1 % (Red)
50 %	48 502	48 502 (100,0 %)	42 169 (86,9 %)	6 333 (13,1 %)	86,9 % (Yellow)
70 %	24 350	24 350 (100,0 %)	23 598 (96,9 %)	752 (3,1 %)	96,9 % (Green)
80 %	15 773	15 773 (100,0 %)	15 438 (97,9 %)	335 (2,1 %)	97,9 % (Green)
85 %	11 434	11 434 (100,0 %)	11 211 (98,0 %)	223 (2,0 %)	98,0 % (Green)
90 %	6 698	6 698 (100,0 %)	6 540 (97,6 %)	158 (2,4 %)	97,6 % (Green)
95 %	1 691	1 691 (100,0 %)	1 635 (96,7 %)	56 (3,3 %)	96,7 % (Green)
100 %	1	1 (100,0 %)	1 (100,0 %)	0 (0,0 %)	100,0 % (Green)
>=105 %	0	---	---	---	---

Fig.6 3D Gamma index values of the Patient #4 plans. Reference dose distribution was the VMAT plan.